

DIRECTIONS D4.1:

Report on realistic test cases for the Belgian offshore energy hub

June 2026

This deliverable forms part of the DIRECTIONS project, funded by the Energy Transition Funds, FOD Economy, Belgium.
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With the support from:

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Chapter 1

Executive summary

This deliverable analyses the use of topological actions in AC/DC grids with large-scale wind integration using a synthetic network model. The general goal is to show how optimizing the grid topology according to given renewable energy sources (RES) capacity factors and electrical demand leads to a reduction in the total generation costs for a given timestep. Firstly, the steady-state optimal power flow (OPF) and grid topology optimization models used to compute the power flows through hybrid AC/DC grids while minimizing the total generation costs are described. The results of these models are compared to determine whether optimizing the grid topology reduces the total generation costs for a set of given timesteps. Secondly, a test case with a synthetic hybrid AC/DC grid with large offshore wind integration is developed. The test case consists of three AC grids with installed capacities taken from the ENTSO-E Ten Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP) 2024 data set. Similarly, the RES and demand time series are taken from the distributed energy scenario for the planning year 2030 (DE 2030), using the climate year 1995 of the same ENTSO-E TYNDP data set. Thirdly, three relevant timesteps are selected from the simulation run for the entire year. These three timesteps correspond to i) an hour with large RES curtailment, ii) the hour with the lowest generation costs and high expected RES curtailment, and iii) the hour with the highest generation cost in the OPF simulations. The results show that grid topology optimization leads to a decrease in generation costs compared to the OPF model when the grid is congested. Therefore, the proposed topological actions reduce RES curtailment during high RES situations and provide similar results to the problem definition without actions during low RES conditions. These results confirm the relevance of grid topology optimization in power systems with high penetrations of renewables, contributing to the current discussion by several TSOs in Europe and ISOs in the United States on the need for better capacity calculation methodologies and grid-enhancing technologies.

This deliverable's content is based on the publication *G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, "Techno-Economic Evaluation of the Use of Topological Actions in an Electrical Energy Hub with Large Penetration of Offshore Wind"*, presented at the CIGRE Montreal International Symposium in October 2025.

Chapter 2

Introduction and motivation

In its decarbonization plans, the European Union foresees 450 GW of installed offshore wind (OFW) capacity in its territory by 2050, with the continent being carbon neutral in the same year [1]. Furthermore, in the Ostend declaration, nine countries on the North Sea committed to building 120 GW and 300 GW OFW by 2030 and 2050, respectively [2]. Due to their economic benefits compared to AC technologies to transmit bulk power over long distances [3], Point-to-Point (PtP) High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) links are currently used to connect OFW farms and renewable energy sources (RES) in general directly to the onshore grid [4]. With many OFW farms built in the upcoming years, electrical energy hubs (EEHs) [5] have been proposed to aggregate multi-GW generation at single offshore network points and interconnect them with different control areas in the European power system. These offshore EEHs are expected to be multi-terminal or meshed high voltage DC grids [4] to increase the power transfer capacity among different control zones in the grid. Moreover, installing only PtP links would cause congestion on the onshore grid if timely onshore grid reinforcements are not installed. These onshore reinforcements have faced and will likely face public opposition [6] in the upcoming years, resulting in delays in their construction and possible cancellation of the entire project. These issues result in delays for RES capacity to come online or increasing RES curtailment as there is less power that can be transmitted to the onshore load centers. For these reasons, building offshore multi-terminal grids offers interconnections to different control areas and power transfer capacity while reducing the need for onshore investments, as the bulk part of the power is transmitted offshore. Recently, adjusting the grid topology to increase the available power transfer capacity [7] in the grid has gained more attention, as i) it is a non-costly action compared to generation redispatch [8] and ii) the inherent uncertainty of RES might lead to significant differences between the forecasted and actual RES realization at a given timestep. Optimizing the grid topology for given RES and electrical demand time series can be

used to relieve congestion and reduce RES curtailment, too, guaranteeing a more efficient utilization of the existing grid infrastructure. This work shows how optimizing the grid topology can reduce RES curtailment and total generation costs on a real-life inspired synthetic hybrid AC/DC grid with an AC/DC EEH with large OFW penetration. The results show how the variability of multi-GW offshore RES generation increases the value of topological actions in the grid. A case study based on the publicly available data from the ENTSO-E TYNDP dataset [9] compares the grid topology optimization model proposed in [10] with the optimal power flow (OPF) model for hybrid AC/DC grids in [11]. This deliverable is organised as follows. Section 2 describes the optimization models used in the deliverable. Section 3 includes the input data for the optimization, introducing the proposed synthetic hybrid AC-DC grid, the main assumptions behind it, and the selected relevant timesteps. Section 4 analyses the results for the busbar splitting (BS) and OPF models, with Section 5 discussing the main findings and concluding the deliverable.

2.1 Comment on realistic test cases for the DIRECTIONS project

All the steady-state test cases developed within the DIRECTIONS project are included as .json files in the [DIRECTIONS_test_cases](#) Github repository.

Chapter 3

Optimization models

3.1 Optimal power flow model

The Optimal Power Flow (OPF) model aims to minimize the generation costs of a set of generators to meet a given demand, represented by electrical loads distributed in the grid, while respecting the physical constraints of power transmission across the grid. These physical constraints are based on Kirchhoff's laws and the thermal limits of the lines, i.e. the maximum power that can flow through them. Moreover, each generator is assigned a cost and a maximum power set point, thus, a merit order is created to meet the electrical demand. A detailed description of all the equations involved in the OPF model can be found in [11, 12], where different mathematical formulations are presented for a bus-branch representation of the power grid. This work relies on both the exact, non-convex AC-OPF formulation for AC/DC grids and the piecewise linear approximation (LPAC) of the OPF model theorised in [12], which was extended to hybrid AC/DC grids in the open-source PowerModelsACDC Julia package [11].

3.2 Grid topology optimization model

The grid topology optimization model used in this deliverable introduces topological actions through a node-breaker representation of AC and DC busbars splitting in the grid [10]. While the objective is still to reduce the total generation costs in the grid, this model offers additional flexibility in adjusting the grid topology to achieve a reduction in generation costs compared to the OPF model. As shown in Figure 3.1, each split busbar is divided into two subparts, with each network element connected to it, which has two switches to potentially connect it to the two subparts. This representation can be compared to a double-busbar model in which each network element

has the freedom to be connected to either part of the split busbar. The outputs of the model include the optimal power set points of each network element in the grid and the status (1 closed, 0 open) of each switch. Note that “switch” is used as a general term for every switching unit in the proposed network.

Figure 3.1: Rationale behind the grid topology optimization model theorised in [10].

As each switch corresponds to a binary variable in the model, the LPAC approximation is used to optimise the topology modelled as a mixed-integer quadratic constraint programming model (MIQCP), which is computationally more efficient compared to nonlinear, non-convex models. For a detailed description of all the sets, parameters, and equations in the model, the reader is referred to [11, 13]. The resulting topology is tested with an AC-OPF formulation, as proposed in [10]. For a detailed description of all the sets, parameters, and equations in the model, the reader is referred to [10].

While in reality system operators likely choose from fixed topologies when splitting a selected busbar, this model can compute the optimal topology for a given RES and load condition and is useful for considering new topology candidates for busbar splitting when new power flows take place in the grid, such as the ones coming from new RES sources and new HVDC links being connected to an existing grid. Necessarily, the optimal topology will need to be tested with dynamic simulations to guarantee the safe operation of the grid in case the topology is modified. Additional constraints such as the maximum amount of possible switching actions in a given timeframe can as well be included in the model.

3.3 Proposed hybrid AC/DC grid

Figure 3.2 displays the real-life inspired synthetic hybrid AC/DC grid proposed in this work. Three AC grids are present in the test case, with AC grid 1 and AC grid 3 connected via one HVDC link and one AC/DC EEH, and AC grid 1 and AC grid 2 connected via AC lines. The AC/DC EEH aggregates the 3.5 GW of OFW farms and is linked to AC grid 1 via an AC connection. In addition, it is connected through an AC/DC converter to a multi-terminal

Figure 3.2: Proposed hybrid AC/DC grid test case with three AC grids and an AC/DC electrical energy hub with offshore wind installed capacity.

DC grid having two HVDC connections to AC grid 1 and AC grid 3. Additionally, 2.2 GW of OFW are connected directly to AC grid 1. This OFW farm has slightly higher generation costs [€/MWh] compared to the other OFW generators shown in Figure 3.2.

The installed capacities of the three AC grids for each generation type are shown in Table 3.1. They refer to the publicly available data in scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995, from the ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9]. The generator types are ordered in Table 3.1 from the cheapest to the most expensive generation type.

The RES and load time series for each grid come from the same DE 2030, climate year 1995, scenario as the generation type. For illustrative purposes, the OFW capacity factor and the demand for each grid for the first 168 hours of the year are shown in Figure 3.3.

Note that while the installed capacities, and the RES and load time series are taken from public data from the ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9], the results presented in the remainder of the deliverable are likely not reflecting the real cost figures in the European power grid. Due to the assumptions of fixed generation costs, 100% availability of each network component, and the zonal approach for each control area grouping all the generators and loads in one node, representing exact generation costs is not the objective of this deliverable. Nevertheless, the same zonal approach is used by ENTSO-E in several studies, and the findings of the deliverable are still relevant in studying the effect of grid topology optimization in the transmission of several

Table 3.1: Installed capacity for each generation type in the three AC grids of the proposed synthetic hybrid AC/DC grid.

Generation type	AC grid 1 [GW]	AC grid 2 [GW]	AC grid 3 [GW]
Solar PV	14.00	23.00	24.35
Wind Onshore	8.00	28.00	22.20
Wind Offshore	5.76	6.20	30.00
Nuclear	3.93	61.73	5.51
Biomass	0.92	2.39	0.00
Gas	35.30	13.13	30.16
Oil	0.02	0.97	0.20
Total Capacity	67.93	135.42	112.42

Figure 3.3: Offshore wind capacity factor and demand for each AC grid for the first 168 hours of ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9] scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995.

gigawatts of power between different control areas in a given power grid.

3.4 Selected timesteps

Both the OPF and BS models are performed for an entire year (8760 hours) using the installed capacities shown in Table 3.2 and the RES and demand time series from scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995, from the ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9]. While with a more detailed and extended grid model selecting the most relevant busbars to be split becomes a challenge, the synthetic nature of the proposed synthetic test case suggests that the busbars to which the EEH and the 2.2 GW OFW farm are connected are the most relevant for this study. These two busbars are highlighted in Figure 3.4, together with the m busbar couplers and all the n network elements involved in the optimization. The total number of switches in the test cases is therefore

Figure 3.4: Representation of the split busbars in the proposed hybrid AC/DC grid test case

$$N_{sw} = 2n + m.$$

Out of the full year simulations for the OPF and BS models, three relevant timesteps are selected in this subsection. Due to space limitations, it is preferred to focus on relevant timesteps to analyse in detail the results of the discussed grid topology optimization models on the test system. The comparison between the results of the OPF and the BS model for the selected timesteps in Table 3.2 is included in the next results section. As the EEH is connected both via AC and DC links to AC grid 1 and the busbars potentially being split are directly linked too to AC grid 1, the timesteps are selected to study the RES (mainly OFW) integration on this part of the grid.

Table 3.2: Selected relevant timesteps to compare the results of the optimal power flow and busbar splitting models for ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9] scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995.

Hour	Reason to select the timestep
571	High RES curtailment
6003	Minimum hourly generation cost, maximum RES curtailment
8760	Maximum hourly generation cost

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Timestep 571

In timestep 571, the OFW capacity factors for AC grids 1, 2, and 3 are respectively 0.95, 0.79, and 0.52, while the onshore wind (ONW) capacity factors are 0.61, 0.45, and 0.13. There is no solar PV generation. As a result of the high OFW capacity factor in AC grid 1, 566 MW of OFW are curtailed. The grid congestion causing the curtailment takes place in both split busbar 1 and split busbar 2 from Figure 3.4. In the OPF formulation, the maximum difference in voltage angles over a line is limited to a fixed value (60° in this work). Given the number of AC lines connected to both split busbar 1 and split busbar 2, the topology restricts the power flows due to the maximum allowable angle limits, resulting in a lower power transfer capacity of the lines. This fact is illustrated by Figure 4.1, which shows the voltage angles of split busbar 1 and split busbar 2 before and after busbar splitting.

The large differences between the OPF and BS values for $va_{1,}$ and between $va_{1,bs}$ and $va_{1',bs}$ after busbar splitting, show that OFW curtailment is reduced by the creation of two parallel paths for the transmission of the OFW farm power. Similarly, splitting split busbar 2, allows the creation of two different paths for power transmission, and lead to a reduction in power import for AC grid 1 from AC grid 2. In this case, the total generation costs of the test system are reduced by 0.15%.

4.2 Timestep 6003

Timestep 6003 is the hour with the lowest total generation costs in the simulated year, due to a combination of low load conditions and high-capacity factors in AC grid 1 and AC grid 2 for both OFW and ONW. In this case, the AC branches connecting split busbar 1 and split busbar 2 are switched off

Figure 4.1: Voltage angles of split busbar 1 and split busbar 2 before and after busbar splitting for timestep 571 from ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9] scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995

to create two parallel paths in the system, as displayed in Figure 4.2. This split in the system allows a reduction of 1.52% in the generation costs. As in the previous timestep, curtailed OFW (1265 MW) is allowed to flow towards AC grid 1 as a result of the BS model. Consequently, there is a reduction in nuclear generation in AC grid 2 and AC grid of respectively 609 MW and 239 MW.

4.3 Timestep 8760

Timestep 8760 is the hour with the highest total generation costs in the simulated year. While the demand is not considerably high, the RES capacity factors for OFW, ONW and solar PV are low (respectively 0.09, 0.04 and 0, 0.09, 0.09 and 0, and 0.27, 0.29 and 0 for AC grid 1, AC grid 2 and AC grid 3). This low-RES generation results in a large power generation from conventional generators and low power transfer from the OFW farms to AC grid 1 and AC grid 3. As a result, the results of the OPF and BS models are equal, with neither split busbar 1 or split busbar 2 being split. While for this particular timestep there is no reduction in total generation costs compared to the OPF model, considerable benefits are computed when extending the simulations for the full year, confirming the value of topological actions in power systems with a high integration of renewables. Note that the proposed test case is rather small and conceptual, and was proposed as an example to show the value of grid topology optimization in a real-life inspired synthetic hy-

Figure 4.2: Optimised grid topology of split busbar 1 and split busbar 2 for timestep 6003 from ENTSO-E TYNDP 2024 [9] scenario DE 2030, climate year 1995.

brid AC/DC grid. The computational time for each timestep is less than 30 seconds for a model with 50 binary variables. The potential benefits of optimizing the topology of a full-sized North Sea grid test case will be computed in the future to assess whether congestion can be solved via topological actions in the power grid.

Chapter 5

Discussion and conclusion

This deliverable elaborates on the use of topological actions in a synthetic hybrid AC/DC grid with large offshore wind integration. Specifically, the topology optimization model developed in [10] is compared against plain OPF models for AC/DC grids to investigate whether optimizing the grid topology leads to reductions in the total generation costs for a given test system. In the three analysed timesteps, optimizing the grid topology is especially useful when there is large RES curtailment in the system due to grid congestion. By opening busbar couplers in selected busbars and connecting network elements to either one or the other busbar being split, a reduction in RES curtailment, therefore a reduction in generation costs, is achieved. When the RES generation, and therefore the grid congestion, is low, there is less incentive to modify the grid topology as the conventional generation and the demand centres connected to the same busbars, and the transmission capacity between the different AC grids is enough to guarantee an optimal power dispatch. Therefore, grid topology optimization is shown to be useful to adapt the grid topology to counteract the RES fluctuating nature and is an effective way to reduce RES curtailment and grid congestion-related costs. In future work, with more detailed grid models, methods to identify effective topological actions will be developed. In addition, strategies to maximise the power transmission capacity by optimizing the grid topology while including RES uncertainty will be explored.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

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